

FREEZING AND THAWING EFFECTS ON THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CONCRETE-CFRP INTERFACES

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ABSTRACT

The recently developed experimental fracture approach known as the single contoured-cantilever beam (SCCB) specimen is implemented to evaluate environmentally conditioned concrete-CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced polymer) interfaces. Fracture studies are conducted on 20 specimens subjected to 50, 100, 150, 200 and 300 cycles of alternate freezing and thawing. Each cycle consists of 2 hours of ramping from room temperature at 20 C to freezing at -20 C, 2 hours of constant freezing at -20 C and then finally ramping from a frozen state back to room temperature (i.e. thaw). The CFRP-bonded concrete specimens are immersed in a calcium chloride solution based on a modified ASTM standard (C672: "Scaling Resistance of Concrete Surfaces Exposed to Deicing Chemicals"). In addition to fracture, weights and strains of the specimens were also recorded initially and at the end of every fifth cycle. Baseline-feedback was provided by control beams, referred to as *companion specimens* (15 total), which were fractured alongside their weathered counterparts at the end of each target age. The durability of the concrete-CFRP interface is finally characterized by comparing relative strain energy release rates (G_{Ic}), corresponding brittleness indices (I), and changes in both weights and strains, as obtained between the weathered and control specimens.

Keywords: fracture, durability, freezing-thawing, CFRP-concrete interface bond

INTRODUCTION

Currently, research in the areas of rehabilitation and/or strengthening of concrete structures is focused on the external bonding of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) plates or fabrics. A concern, however, exists with the long-term reliable performance of the interface bond that is centrally critical to the successful application of this technology.

Until recently, there were no available methods to rigorously evaluate the interface bond strength and integrity for concrete structures externally reinforced with FRP materials. Existing large-scale tests of structural components used for stiffness and strength evaluations, on the one hand, are ill suited for detecting delamination effects. On the other, small-scale tests only provide average interface strength properties that neither describe failure mechanisms nor provide fracture toughness data. In an effort to resolve this dilemma, the new Fracture Mechanics test methodology referred to as the single contoured-cantilever beam (SCCB; see Boyajian et al., 2000, 2002a, and 2002b), conceived and fashioned after the established double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen, is here implemented to study the effects of freezing and thawing on concrete-CFRP interfaces—a protocol chosen to simulate the harsh wintry conditions experienced in many parts of the world wherein deicing agents (i.e. salts) are dispersed onto highways as a measure to safeguard against ice-formation.

A total of 20 CFRP-bonded concrete specimens (see Fig. 1) were inverted (see Fig. 2) in specially designed stainless steel trays filled with calcium chloride (CaCl_2 —abbreviated herein as CC) solution up to the level of the interface (Fig. 1(a)). The purpose for doing this was to focus the degradative media to this region of interest, and thus prevent the bulk substrate (Fig. 1(b)) from any undue deterioration.

Though there is no available standard practice for the testing of concrete-FRP interfaces subjected to freeze-thaw conditioning under chloride solution, ASTM C672 and C666 were reviewed and modified appropriately in arriving at the formulation of the present protocol. The aforementioned specimens underwent 5-age categories of 50, 100, 150, 200, and 300 freeze-thaw cycling in an environmental chamber (see Fig. 3), at which time the beams were destructively fractured to obtain the critical strain energy release rate values, denoted G_{Ic} (Eq. [1]). Here, each cycle consists of 6 hours, divided into three equal frames of time, the first and last of which involve ramping from room temperature (20 C) to a determined freeze state (-20 C) and vice-versa, respectively, and the middle segment, serving as a connective between the two by maintaining the achieved condition of freezing (-20 C) uniformly throughout its duration (see Fig. 4 for a schematic representation).

$$[1] \quad G_{Ic} = \frac{P_c^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da}$$

Following SCCB fracture-testing at each of the five target ages, interface degradations were computed relative to the G_{Ic} values of the control, i.e. *companion*, specimens. The scientifically-based, statistical procedure of the *head-* (i.e. topmost) and *set-* (i.e. all) load approaches developed by Boyajian et al. (2002a) were used to this end, from which conclusive G_{Ic} values were rendered by the averaging of such *admissible* results.

Figure 1 CFRP-bonded concrete specimen—(a) front view, (b) side view

Figure 2 Picture of FT beams inverted in stainless steel trays

MATERIALS

Three different types of materials were used in fabricating the CFRP-bonded concrete specimens (Fig. 1) of this study. Starting from the top, these include the:

- CFRP strip (MBrace CF130 tow (high tensile))
- MBrace primer/saturant epoxy resins
- Concrete substrate

CFRP Strip

MBrace CF130 high tensile, unidirectional, carbon fiber strips (MBrace Composite Strengthening System, 1998) were used at the interface, with a modulus of elasticity, $E_{CF} = 228$ GPa (33 Msi), an ultimate -strength and -strain of 4.3 GPa (0.62 Msi) and 1.67%, a fiber volume fraction range of $V_f = 20\% - 22\%$, a thickness, $t = 0.16$ mm/ply (0.0065 in/ply), and a width consisting of 1700 fibers/mm (43,200 fibers/in).

Primer/Saturant

A two-component epoxy resin, known as the MBrace primer, was first applied to the concrete bonding surface (see Fig. 1(a)) to penetrate the pores and promote the quality of the bond. The primer has a modulus of elasticity, $E_p = 0.72$ GPa (0.104 Msi), a yield -stress and -strain of 14 MPa (2100 psi) and 4%, and a Poisson's ratio, $\nu_p = 0.48$. After allowing the primer to cure for 24 hours, a two-component epoxy resin, known as the MBrace saturant, was applied both to the primed concrete bonding surface as well as the precut carbon fiber strips. The saturated CFRP tow was then attached to the concrete substrate, forming what is being termed herein as the CFRP-bonded concrete specimen (Fig. 1). The saturant has a modulus of elasticity, $E_s = 3$ GPa (0.440 Msi), a yield -stress and -strain of 54 MPa (7800 psi) and 2.5%, and a Poisson's ratio, $\nu_s = 0.40$.

Concrete Substrate

Casting of the concrete beams was performed at the concrete laboratory of West Virginia University. ASTM Type I portland cement was used with a water-cement mixture proportioning ratio of 0.5, 6% air, and locally available natural sand and #8 pea-gravel aggregates. The mean 28-day compressive strength of the concrete was found to be 51.6 MPa (7480 psi) with a standard deviation of 2.1 MPa (310 psi).

Figure 3 Picture of the CSZ (ZH-16) environmental chamber

Figure 4 Freeze-thaw cycling scheme

FREEZE-THAW FRACTURE TEST RESULTS

Degradation resulting from freezing and thawing occurs whenever moisture within the concrete freezes and consequently expands in volume (approximately by 9%) leading to the development of osmotic and hydraulic pressures. Such effects are responsible for the cracking and rupturing of both the hardened cement paste and aggregate particles, which, moreover, become exacerbated in the presence of deicing agents, i.e. salts. A secondary form of degradation eventuated by these thawing saline environments, concerning, of course, reinforced concrete (RC) structures, is the adverse reaction of corrosion that precipitates with the internal steel reinforcement.

In this study, 20 CFRP-bonded concrete beams (Fig. 1) were subjected to a maximum of 300 cycles of alternate freeze-thaw cycling (Fig. 4) under a calcium chloride (CC) solution in accordance with ASTM C672. The results of the SCCB fracture tests, expressed in terms of the Mode I, initiation and arrestment, critical strain energy release rates, G_{Ic}^i and G_{Ic}^a , respectively, are presented in Table 1. Presented here are also the brittleness indices (Eq. 2), I —a quantitative normalization of the energy being released (i.e. lost) during a period of rapid crack growth with respect to the energy that was stored in the joint just at the onset of crack-initiation (Ebewele, River and Koutsky, 1986). Thus,

$$[2] \quad I = \frac{G_{Ic}^i - G_{Ic}^a}{G_{Ic}^i}$$

Accordingly, an ideally brittle material that fails suddenly and completely will have an index value of $I = 1$, since $G_{Ic}^a = 0$. On the other hand, an ideally plastic material that fails by continuous tearing and having indistinct G_{Ic}^i and G_{Ic}^a energies will have an index

value of $I = 0$. Thus, larger I values indicate abrupt and unstable crack growths whereas smaller ones signify cracks progressing more slowly and in slighter increments. In their wood fracture studies, River and Okkonen (1993) reported a value of $I = 0.43$ as representing a strong/moderately unstable crack, while a value of $I = 0.06$ conveyed a more stable form of crack propagation.

Table 1 Averaged conclusive freeze-thaw fracture results (unit: J/m^2)

	50 cycles	100 cycles	150 cycles	200 cycles	300 cycles
(1) G_{Ic}^i/FTC^*	568/604	542/632	604/738	550/776	491/811
(2) G_{Ic}^a/FTC^*	554/586	522/605	592/718	544/764	477/772
% (1),(2)	94%,94%	86%,86%	82%,82%	71%,71%	60%,62%
I [no unit]	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.03

* FTC = ave. freeze-thaw companion results

Note that the freeze-thaw cracking behavior in this study can be described as being stable due to the low brittleness index (averaged, see Table 1)— $I_{ave} = 0.02$. As such, the freeze-thaw interface may thus be characterized as being *strain rate insensitive*—that is, the nature of cracking extends at a (fairly) constant value of strain energy release rate.

As for the values of fracture toughness, inspection of the bar graphs (see Fig. 5) reveals a declining trend of relative percentage G_{Ic} reductions, as would be expected due to the

⁺Reductions computed relative to companion values;

*Interpolated companion value for Cycle-100

Figure 5 Averaged conclusive CC freeze-thaw % G_{Ic} reductions

adverse CC/freeze-thaw regime. The average variation between head and set G_{Ic} percentage reductions (refer to Boyajian et al., 2002a) for the CC exposure scheme was found to be 5%, with maximum and minimum deviations of 13% and 1% for the 200th cycle and 100th/150th cycle arrestment-based cases.

After the complete duration of aging at 300 cycles, head and set initiation- and arrestment- based reductions in fracture toughness values for the CC regime revealed results of 60% and 62% (averaged), respectively. This demonstrates that the CFRP-concrete interface reliability may be characterized as being *less than two-thirds* as effectual as it would have otherwise been were it not subjected to such attack.

SECONDARY INTERFACE-BOND CHARACTERIZATIONS

Weight Changes

A total of 23 specimens were used to measure weight-variations: 3 plain (i.e. specimens without CFRP at the interface and subjected to the freeze-thaw aging-protocol), 10 companion (i.e. controls), and 10 actual (i.e. CFRP-bonded concrete specimens subjected to the FT aging-protocol and SCCB fracture) beams. Though the overall weight changes resulting from the specimens were quite slight—the maximum gain being only 3.21% at the 200th cycle (see Fig. 6)—some pertinent observations are worth mentioning.

Firstly, the increases in weight are attributable to primarily: (1) the considerable salt crystallization and deposition in the specimens' open pores, and (2) the corrosion of the internal steel reinforcement (not of the pitting type). Concerning the latter point, recall that the specimens were *partially* submerged—up to the level of the interface (see Fig. 2)—in a calcium chloride (CC) solution. Had the beams been *completely* immersed in the CC bath, they most certainly would have been deprived of the vital component of oxygen (O₂)—a necessary condition if the internal steel-reinforcing members are to rust (FeO₂).

Considering now the trends displayed in Fig. 6, it is seen that the actual specimens' weight gains are greater than their plain counterparts. This is attributed to the actual beams' higher potential for water uptake within the saturant-and-CFRP layer. The rate of weight gain achieved by the actual beams is also unchanging for 150 cycles, after which, this trend essentially stabilizes. This conforms to both the qualitative post- and pre-fracture observations (*results that have not been presented in this paper due to space constraints*) that asserted cycle-150 as a pivotal point of demarcation between specimen -soundness and -degradation. It is speculated that in this first-half period of aging, i.e. up to cycle-150, all the weight gains were due to moisture uptake and salt-crystallization within the exposed concrete regions and the saturant-and-CFRP layer. In the second-half, when the first of these effects is believed to have become equilibrated, however, the loss in concrete mass due to spalling and the initiating ferric oxide (responsible for causing reinforcement corrosion) coupled with a continuance of salt-crystallization, was seemingly found to be tantamount. (The erosive, CC/freeze-thaw action apparently overpowered the *fortifying* effect of the CFRP reinforcement in the actual specimens.) The same thing is noted for the plain specimens, except that the latter processes, i.e. those corresponding to weight-gains, were more substantial than the spalling concrete, thus explaining the moderately increasing slope at cycle-300.

Figure 6 Percent average weight changes of the CC/freeze-thaw *plain*, *companion*, and *actual* beams

Strain Changes

The same 23 specimens used for measuring weights were also used to gauge the possible occurrence of any differential movement between the CFRP composites and the underlying concrete substrates. Variations in strains (see Fig. 7) were recorded through the use of a demountable mechanical strain gauge (DEMEC) instrument, outfitted with a digital dial gauge sensitive to 0.01 mm (0.0005").

In order to get a sense of what may be deemed as either significant or insignificant concerning the reported microstrains, the tensile strength of concrete is considered (or assumed) as a critical parameter. The American Concrete Institute (ACI 363R-92, Eq. 5-3, p. 25, 1992) reports that the split-tensile strength (an indirect measure of tensile strength), f_{sp}' (in units of MPa), can be taken as $f_{sp}' = 0.59 \cdot (f_c')^{1/2}$, valid for $21 \leq f_c' \leq 83$ MPa (or, equivalently, for f_c' given in units of psi, $f_{sp}' = 7.4 \cdot (f_c')^{1/2}$, valid for $3000 \leq f_c' \leq 12,000$ psi). Thus, in keeping with SI units,

$$[3] \quad f_{sp}' = 0.59 \cdot (f_c')^{1/2} \quad [\text{in MPa}]$$

where the mean 28-day compressive strength of the concrete used in this study was found to be $f_c' = 51.6$ MPa (=7480 psi). Therefore, with respect to this concrete,

$$[3'] \quad f_{sp}' = 4.24 \text{ MPa}$$

Correspondingly, the tensile *stress* of the concrete that has developed at the interface due to the differential strain, may then be computed from Hooke's law as:

$$[4] \quad \sigma_t = E_c \cdot \varepsilon$$

where E_c is given by the ACI code requirements (318R-92, Sec. 8.5.1, p. 79, 1992):

$$[5] \quad E_c = 57,000 \cdot (f_c')^{1/2} \quad [f_c' \text{ in psi}]$$

and $\varepsilon = \text{strain} = 10^6$ microstrains (note: microstrains may be abbreviated as $\mu\varepsilon$). Thus, $E_c = 4.93 \times 10^6$ psi, which when converted to SI units is:

$$[5'] \quad E_c = 33,991 \text{ MPa}$$

By considering the maximum differential microstrain of the freeze-thaw specimens (see Fig. 7), 49 $\mu\varepsilon$, the resulting stress (by Eq. [4]) is therefore found to be:

$$[4'] \quad \sigma_{t,FT} = 1.67 \text{ MPa}$$

Comparing this *stress* value with the assumed tolerable interfacial *strength* (cited in [3']), reveals a factor in excess of 2.5. Therefore, under similar conditions and durations of CC/freeze-thaw exposure, it can safely be assumed that no appreciable development of strain will form at the CFRP-concrete interface.

Figure 7 Microstrains of the *CC/freeze-thaw* beams

CONCLUSIONS

- The concrete-CFRP interface as subjected to freezing and thawing was found to render a characteristically strain rate insensitive phenomenon, i.e. the crack propagation proceeds in a stable manner.
- After the complete duration of aging at 300 cycles, SCCB fracture testing revealed that the interface integrity had been compromised to being less than two-thirds as efficient, had it not been subjected to such attack.
- From weight measurements along with visual observations, cycle-150 was found to be a pivotal point of demarcation between specimen-soundness and -degradation.
- There was no appreciable development of strain at the concrete-CFRP interface ($f_{sp}'/\sigma_{t,FT} > 2.5$) throughout the duration of the freeze-thaw aging protocol.

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